

Raman Effect and Molecular Structure. Part I. The Structure of the Guanidinium Ion.

BY JAGANNATH GUPTA.

It is well known that guanidine, $\text{HN}=\text{C}(\text{NH}_2)_2$, in spite of its containing two amino groups, is a strong mono-acid base. The corresponding ion, therefore, has the apparent possibility of assuming any of the three following structures :

(I)

(II)

(III)

Investigations on the crystal structures of guanidinium halides have served to clear up the question only partially. Theilacker (*Z. Krist.*, 1935, **90A**, 51, 256) has shown that in the guanidinium ion, all the three nitrogen atoms are crystallographically equivalent and the ionic character can not be associated with any particular nitrogen atom. This result, therefore, cancels the probability of structure (I), although it can not decide between structure (II), and a resonance structure between the three double bonded forms of type (III).

It is evident that the problem is intimately connected with the question, whether or not an imino group can function as a basic unit in neutralisation reactions. Although the basic activity of the imino group is least expected in a molecule like guanidine, which already contains two other amino groups, the consistently mono-acidic character of the base raises this unusual possibility. It was thought that a study of the Raman effect of the ion might throw some light on the problem, and the results of the investigations are described and discussed in the present paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Water for preparing solutions.—Distilled water was thrice redistilled in vacuum to render it free from dust and fluorescent impurities.

Guanidine Nitrate.—The pure substance was recrystallised from distilled water containing a little nitric acid and the crystals washed several times with the redistilled water. A saturated solution (30 c. c.) was then prepared and kept over 0.5 g. of activated charcoal* (prepared from extra pure glucose) for several hours. About 1 g. of extra pure crystallised potassium bromide was added †, and the solution filtered repeatedly through double folds of gravimetric filter papers. The filtrate was finally run directly into the Wood's tube, when the solution was ready for exposure.

Guanidine Hydrochloride.—Pure guanidine carbonate was gradually added to hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) kept cooled in water, keeping excess of acid. The solution, after warming on the water-bath to remove all carbon dioxide, was filtered and allowed to crystallise in a desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid. The mother liquor was drained off from the crystals by suction and the latter washed with chemically pure concentrated hydrochloric acid. The pure crystals thus obtained were dissolved in a very small quantity of water, containing a little pure HCl to prevent hydrolysis. KBr (1 g.) was added to the solution which was then repeatedly filtered as before till free from any suspended impurities. The tubes were illuminated by the condenser method using a quartz mercury arc lamp as the source of illumination. The illumination was increased with a metal reflector. A solution (4%) of *m*-dinitrobenzene in benzene was used to cut off the 4046 Å group of mercury lines, and a dilute solution of *o*-cresolphthalein in NaOH to remove the faint mercury bands to the shorter wave-length side of the 4916 Å mercury line, for unequivocal detection of faint Raman lines in this region.

For the polarisation experiment, the arrangement described by the present author in a previous paper (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1936, 10, 313) was used. The results are shown in the following table.

* Kindly supplied by the Department of Physical Chemistry.

Repeated experiments have shown that the addition of small quantities of KBr or KI effectively reduces the continuous background usually observed in the scattered spectrum of aqueous solutions. The actual part played by the salt is not clear.

Guanidine nitrate soln.		Guanidine hydrochloride soln.		
$\Delta\nu$.	Intensity and width of lines (visual).	$\Delta\nu$.	Intensity and width of lines.	Polarisation characters.
520	1	522	1	$\rho > 0.5$
997	3	995	4	$\rho < 0.2$
1045	3			
1350	1 b			
1610	1 b	1620	$\frac{1}{2}$ b	$\rho > 0.5$

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS.

As can be seen from the preceding table, the Raman lines attributable to the guanidinium ion are in the region of 520, 1000 and 1620 wave-numbers. The extra lines at 1045 and 1350 wave-numbers are associated with the vibrations of the NO_3^- ion (cf. Nisi, *Proc. Phys. Math. Soc. Japan*, 1933, 15, 114). The line at 995 cm^{-1} , attributed to guanidinium ion is intense, sharp and strongly polarised.

From the theory of the origin of Raman scattering, it is well known that those vibrations, which are completely symmetrical, *i.e.*, which are not attended with any change in the electric moment of the molecule, and are "forbidden" in the infra-red absorption spectra, give rise to the most intense Raman lines of very small depolarisation factors. It can, therefore, be asserted with some confidence that the line at 995 cm^{-1} owes its origin to the totally symmetrical vibration of three NH_2 -groups against the carbon atom at their centre, much like the oscillations of the oxygen atoms against the central C and N atoms in carbonates and nitrates respectively. The low value of the frequency shift, *viz.*, about 1000 wave-numbers, rules out the possibility of the double bonded resonance structure (III) and lends every support to the formula $\text{H}_2\text{N}-\overset{+}{\text{C}}\begin{matrix} \text{NH}_2 \\ \text{NH}_2 \end{matrix}$ (II).

The faint band in the region of 1620 wave-numbers goes to indicate that the ions may not all be of one form but may possess a small percentage of the form containing the double bond (III), inasmuch

as the value of the shift is close to the value 1650-cm^{-1} , attributed to the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group, as shown in the oximes (cf. Bonino and Manzoni-Ansidei, *Mem. Accad. Italia*, 1933, **4**, 759; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1933, **22B**, 169) in dicyandiamide (cf. Dadiou and Kohlrausch, *Monatsh.*, 1931, **57**, 225) etc. Judging from the fact that the line at 1650 cm^{-1} which appears in compounds containing $\text{C}=\text{N}$ grouping is usually strong, it appears from the very feeble intensity of the line at about 1620 cm^{-1} in the guanidinium ion, that the percentage of molecules containing the double bonded structure is certainly not large in the solution. The possibility of the line coming from guanidine itself which might have been formed by hydrolysis should not also be overlooked, inasmuch as the intensity of the line is less in an acid solution of the hydrochloride than in a neutral solution of the nitrate.

The next point of particular interest is to examine whether any information regarding the spatial distribution of the atoms can be deduced from theoretical considerations, e.g., whether the C atom lies in the same plane as that containing the three N atoms, or otherwise. According to the polarisability theory of the origin of Raman lines as developed by Placzek (*Handbuch der Radiologie*, Vol. VI, Leipzig, 1934) on the symmetry properties of molecules, a molecule of the type YX_3 gives rise to the following fundamental frequencies:

(a) When Y lies in a plane different from that containing the three X atoms (symmetry C_{3v})—two totally symmetric oscillations and two degenerate, all of which are active both in Raman scattering and infra-red absorption.

(b) When Y lies in the same plane as containing the three X atoms (symmetry D_{3h})—one totally symmetric oscillation, active in Raman scattering and forbidden in infra-red absorption, one antisymmetric oscillation, in Raman scattering generally forbidden, and two degenerate, symmetrical to the plane, active in Raman scattering, but usually do not give rise to so sharp and intense Raman lines as symmetric vibrations do.

In the Raman spectra of a molecule of the type (b), therefore, there are expected three lines, one strong and highly polarised, due to the totally symmetric oscillation, and two less intense lines, completely depolarised, i.e., having $\rho=6, 7$.

The experimental results show only one strongly polarised Raman line and not two. On the basis of Placzek's theoretical considerations,

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A. Raman spectra of guanidine hydrochloride in water.

B. Polarisation of the 995 line.

(i) Weak component.

(I) Strong component.

it can therefore be definitely stated that the guanidinium ion possesses a planar structure.

The ion, therefore, completely resembles the nitrate or the carbonate ion, where three similar atoms are at the three corners of an equilateral triangle and the central N or the C atom is at the intersection of the medians. This is in complete agreement with the conclusions arrived at by Theilacker from X'ray analysis and investigations of the optical properties of crystals of guanidinium iodide (*Z. Krist.*, 1935, **90A**, 51, 77).

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PALIT CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

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